

“UCHINCHI RENESSANS POYDEVORINI QO‘YISHDA FILOLOGIK TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI”

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THE FEATURES OF TEACHING UZBEK AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO CHINESE STUDENTS

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Abstract: *In recent years, Uzbekistan has vigorously developed the national language, issued various policies to improve the Uzbek language system, and promoted the Uzbek language overseas. As an important strategic partner of Uzbekistan, China attaches great importance to cultural exchanges with Uzbekistan. This article discusses the features of teaching Uzbek language as a foreign language to Chinese students, taking into account the specifics of the Chinese language and the peculiarities of the Chinese mentality. The relevance of the study is due to the constantly growing interest in the Uzbek language in the Chinese society in connection with a noticeable increase in the number of all kinds of contacts between Uzbekistan and China. Our proposed work is based on the search for optimal ways to increase the effectiveness of teaching Uzbek as a foreign language to Chinese students. The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate and develop a phased system for teaching Uzbek as a foreign language to Chinese students. The main research methods were the analysis of the academic literature on the methodology of teaching Uzbek language as a foreign language, as well as diagnostic methods, including observation, description, conversation, questioning, testing, and methods of statistical data processing. The article contains comparative analyzes of linguistic systems in Uzbek and Chinese. On the example of practical material for teaching phrase logical units in Uzbek, containing zoonyms, the role of the native language in understanding the educational material at the early stage of training is shown.*

Keywords: *Uzbek as a foreign language, Chinese mentality, Uzbekistan, China, educational system, first language.*

Introduction

In December 2017, Uzbek President Mirziyoyev inspected the Tashkent State Uzbek Language and Literature University and proposed: “The Uzbek language must be widely disseminated to the world, revealing its richness, respecting and loving the Uzbek language.”[7]

In recent years, Uzbek has been initially promoted worldwide, not only in Turkic-speaking countries and Central Asian countries, but also attracted the attention of other countries. As one of Uzbekistan's most important partners, China is committed to developing cooperation with Uzbekistan in political, economic, cultural and other fields. In terms of economic and trade cooperation, in 2022, the bilateral trade volume between China and Uzbekistan will be 99.78 billion dollars, an increase of 21.8% year-on-year. Among them, China exported US77.504 billion, an increase of 27.7% year-on-year, and China imported US22.276 billion, an increase of 5.6% year-on-year.[4] The number of Chinese companies in Uzbekistan is increasing day

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by day, and the demand for Uzbek is rapidly increasing. The other reason why increasing number of Chinese people choose to study Uzbek language lies in the fact that the amount of Russian speakers is becoming less and less in Uzbekistan, which absolutely leads to the spread of Uzbek language not only in the territories of Uzbekistan, but also all over the world.

The implementation of Uzbekistan’s language policy today is mainly reflected in the following aspects: 1) Uzbekistan’s language reform is the concrete embodiment of the national development strategy and an important driving force for national modernization. The ultimate goal of the reform is to transform the national language into national values so that it can truly play the role of unifying the various ethnic groups in the country. The introduction and implementation of a series of language policies will greatly enhance the inherent strength of Uzbek language development. 2) Comprehensively and fundamentally improve the role and authority of the Uzbek language and the level of modernization of the Uzbek language, once again demonstrating the Uzbek government’s determination to de-Russify and westernize, as well as his confidence in joining the B Turkic information space. The Parliament of Uzbekistan will strengthen the revision of the new version of the National Language Law, the purpose of which is to ensure the development of the national language and the comprehensive transition to romanization. According to the plan, Uzbekistan will fully transition to the new alphabet by January 1, 2023. Although the new draft alphabet is still under discussion, only the plan will be determined. It will speed up the pace of change in the chaotic situation of “two letters and two languages”. 3) The Uzbek government attaches special importance to the establishment of norms and rules for Uzbek literature and language. The dissemination of Uzbek literature and language to the broadest audience through the mass media can effectively improve the people’s mastery and use of the national language, so as to achieve the purpose of improving the people’s language and culture. 4) Youth are the main force in the development of the national language, inheriting and disseminating the best achievements of Uzbek national spirit and traditional culture. In 2021 the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to fundamentally improve the spiritual education work system” inferred that improving knowledge of teenagers will effectively promote the realization of Uzbekistan's new language policy goals.[6, p.27]

During the China - Central Asia summit of 2023, a mechanism for the China—Central Asian Ministers of Education meeting was also established. These policies will provide more and more platforms for cultural and educational

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cooperation between China and Uzbekistan and promote language and cultural exchanges between the two countries.[3] In January of 2024, the Forum of China - Uzbekistan universities was held in Beijing, on the period of which a huge number of agreements between universities were signed.

Nowadays, there are a small number of schools offering Uzbek majors in China, including Beijing Foreign Studies University, Minzu University of China, Shanghai Foreign Studies University and Luoyang Foreign Language School. Among them, there are Chinese teachers bringing Uzbek lessons in Beijing Foreign Studies University, Minzu University of China and Luoyang Foreign Language School, while other schools hire Uzbek teachers to attend classes. In terms of professional training, Beijing Foreign Studies University basically recruits a group of Uzbek language students every four years, each time recruiting about 7 students; Minzu University of China recruits more than ten students every year, because of the special nature of this university, the students are basically mainly Uyghurs. Since Uzbek and Uyghur language belong to the same branch of the Turkic language family, Uyghur students have a natural language advantage in learning Uzbek. The way Chinese universities train Uzbek majors is much the same, basically based on the “Russian+Uzbek” model, that is, Uzbek teaching is carried out on the basis of Russian teaching. Students usually only study Russian in the first grade, start Uzbek classes in the second grade, and have the opportunity to exchange studies in Uzbekistan through the national scholarship program in the third grade. This kind of training method has certain advantages, mainly for the following reasons: First of all, Russian still has the status of an inter-ethnic communicative language in Uzbekistan, and Uzbeks often use Russian for communication in formal occasions and daily life. Secondly, some of the words and grammar in Uzbek come from Russian. If there is no Russian foundation, it will be difficult to understand and learn Uzbek. Therefore, Uzbek language teaching should be individualized and adjusted and improved according to the ethnic characteristics and learning habits of Chinese students.

Features of the Chinese mentality

As practice shows, a teacher working with Chinese students should know, at least, the mentality of the students, have an idea of the traditions and customs of the country where the young people came from. Chinese culture is fundamentally different from Western culture, which is determined by the centuries-old traditional collectivist culture of Eastern society. The teacher should take into account such national characteristics of the Chinese people as diligence, modesty, purposefulness, open character. At the same time, Chinese students believe that their success or

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failure in their studies depends on the teacher. Therefore, the teacher has a great responsibility in the learning process. It is necessary that students see the teacher as a friendly, calm, professional person.

The first difficulties in learning affect already at the first stage, when getting acquainted with the Uzbek alphabet in the section “Phonetics”. For the Chinese, Uzbek letters do not carry any information, unlike visual and figurative Chinese characters. The teacher should give information about the sound-letter system of the Uzbek language and preferably in Chinese. In Chinese, there are no letters that are pronounced as “g” and “x”, which causes great difficulties in pronouncing this sound. In teaching the Uzbek language, it is very difficult for beginners to master the letter “r”. They can read it as [l]. When a teacher teaches students correct pronunciation, he should not only give students the opportunity to imitate and read them repeatedly and automatically, but also use Chinese to explain the position of the tip of the tongue, the shape of the lips, correct breathing. In this case, students can easily understand this phonetic sign. The same is true when explaining the pronunciation of vowels, consonants and compound words .

The Chinese learning system is based on constant memorization. This method of teaching can be actively used when practicing the sounds of the Uzbek language. It is difficult for Chinese students to assimilate the sound of [r], as well as distinguish between [x] and [h], [g] and [g‘]. In most cases, phonetic difficulties are mainly associated with the processes of assimilation and accommodation of sounds. Savvina G.V., a master’s student of the RCT Department, has a positive experience in phonetics with Chinese students. In her manual, G.V. Savvina actively uses not only pedagogical, methodological, but also speech therapy technologies. When working on such a type of speech activity as "listening", it is very important to use text.

Chinese students in the classroom always focus on thinking, They think for a long time in order to correctly understand the educational material. In this regard, the teacher should devote more time to thinking about new material, its comprehension. Vocabulary work plays a special role in the educational process as one of the most important forms of educational activity.

When implementing such a type of speech activity as “speaking”, it is desirable that in everyday life Chinese students communicate with their compatriots in Uzbek. However, this does not always work out, so the teacher builds the learning process so that all types of speech activity are organically connected. An important stage in mastering the Uzbek language is such a type of speech activity as “reading”.

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As practice shows, it is effective to refer to the text of fiction. It should be adapted, but not emasculated educational material. It should provide information about the history, epoch, culture, traditions, customs of Uzbekistan, reflected in the text of fiction. In addition, such a text is an exemplary material of correct Uzbek speech, which reflects all grammatical situations. For all its importance, working with text causes great difficulties for Chinese students. This is due to the fact that Chinese students do not understand the logic of the text, its causal, associative, and sometimes intuitive connections. They do not know how to perform logical operations, and elementary questions from the teacher can cause difficulties. Recently, as a result of the search for effective techniques, ways, and means of teaching the Uzbek language in the Chinese audience, the method of including the text of fiction in the educational process using graphic and symbolic analysis has found application. As practice has shown, this technique has justified itself. Students began to speak better, their vocabulary expanded, the process of developing oral coherent speech improved, interest in the Uzbek language, Uzbek culture, and the history of Uzbekistan increased.

The objective obstacles for Chinese students to learn Uzbek are mainly reflected in the lack of learning materials, insufficient teachers, and few opportunities for language practice. There is no Uzbek-Chinese dictionary in the true sense in China that has been publicly published. Electronic dictionaries published on the Internet often do not have a complete thesaurus, nor can they provide examples and explanations of vocabulary use. Without reference books, students cannot easily understand and use the language. In terms of teaching materials, the most authoritative Uzbek textbook currently recognized in China is the “*Uzbek Language Course*” prepared by Teacher Gulibanum of Minzu University of China, which provides Uzbek beginners with a more comprehensive introduction to Uzbek phonetics, grammar and vocabulary from scratch, and is also equipped with Uzbekistan’s national conditions and culture[2, p.16]. Learning a foreign language is inseparable from the influence of the language environment. At present, the higher education cooperation between China and Uzbekistan mainly lies in Uzbek students coming to China as exchange students, and few Chinese students go to Uzbekistan to exchange just for learning Uzbek. However, it is obvious that in the near future, as Uzbekistan’s national strength continues to increase, Uzbek language and culture will become more and more well-known and loved by the international community, and more Chinese will be interested in Uzbek language learning.

The role of the native language at the initial stage of teaching Uzbek as a

foreign language in the Chinese audience

In the research of scientists, the question often arises: “Is it necessary to use the native language when teaching the Uzbek language? If yes, to what extent and when?”. As practice has shown, the appeal to the native language acquires special importance at the initial stage of learning Uzbek as a foreign language in conditions when the Uzbek language cannot yet perform the required functions. The native language can be used not only as a means of managing the educational process: to convey the discussion of problematic issues, organizational information, recommendations on the organization of the educational process, etc., but in the process itself, for a better understanding of the educational situation, clarifying a particular term of the assignment and instructions, which contributes to an adequate understanding of the educational material. The use of Chinese Uzbek and Uygur language is also available in studying Uzbek as a comparative method.[1, p.57]

The use of Uzbek and Chinese phraseological units in the classroom played an important role in the development of oral coherent speech in the Uzbek language. A comparative comparison of these types of folklore helps to see the general and nationally specific. Uzbek and Chinese phraseological units have a common structure, they are characterized by allegory. But there are differences. This is most clearly shown in the examples. First of all, we can say that some phraseological units are of a general nature and they are identical in translation.

The proverbs of the two countries are similar in form and content. In terms of the number of sentences, the proverbs of both countries are dominated by double sentences, accounting for more than 94%. From the perspective of semantic relations, there are eight types of complex sentences, such as juxtaposition and sequential inheritance. From the point of view of rhetoric devices, they are good at using metaphors, personification and other figures of speech; From the animal image, cattle, horses, pigs, sheep and other common animals tend to be the same. From the perspective of cultural significance, the people of the two countries share some common value judgment and aesthetic orientation, such as loving motherland and hometown, praising people and heroes, encouraging diligence and trustworthiness, unity, and belittling laziness and deception.

For example, there are a few Chinese and Uzbek phrases are quite same not only in forms but also in meanings, such as:

Olis yo‘l otni sinar, og‘ir yo‘l mardni sinar.

路遥知马力，日久见人心。

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Yetti o‘ylab bir kes.

三思而后行。

Chinese and Uzbek phraseological units with zoonyms have their own characteristics, which are determined by national culture and mentality. When translating phraseological units into another language, it is necessary to take into account the comparability of the cultural meanings encoded in them.[5, p.47]

Conclusion

The research results of this paper have certain theoretical and practical significance, and deepening the study of Uzbek is conducive to collaborative development at home and abroad.

-Deepening cultural cooperation between the two countries and promoting civil exchanges are of great significance for the study of cross-border ethnic issues.

-Promote the development of Uzbek language and help the spread of Uzbek civilization.

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